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HISTORY OF GLOBALIZATION AND PHILOSOPHY OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the history of the origin of globalization and the philosophers, scientists and their philosophical ideas that contributed to its origin. In addition, it is about the goals and principles of sustainable development.

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Globalization (globalization) is derived from the Latin word "glob", which means "rounding". It is used to explain the transformation of the globe, the globe, into a whole sphere, a globe, at the disposal of mankind due to scientific and technical achievements. The word "global" means "general" in French and "globe" in Latin. Therefore, the concept of globalism in these two senses includes big problems directly related to the life and destiny of mankind, "planetary", "worldly" problems, prospects of global development.

Giddins coined the phrase "globalization" for the first time in 1960. Before the 1990s of the 20th century, this phrase was hardly ever used. R. Robertson, an American sociologist, first used the term "globalization" in 1985. Since 1981, economists have first used the word "globalization." However, Charles Taz Russell, an American scientist, thoroughly explained the meaning and notion of this phrase in the middle of 1990.

In an essay that appeared in the "Harvard Business Review" magazine in 1983, American scientist T. Levitt coined the term "Globalization" for the first time. The processes of integration of multiple product markets created by major multinational firms were referred to as "globalization" by T. Levitt. The economic effects of the process of globalization are discussed in this definition. During his time, French philosopher René Descartes penned the following: "Clarify the meaning of concepts and this will save half of humanity from going astray." In this regard, we shall first attempt to define the term "globalization" and its etymological meaning. You can define this word as follows: The interaction of the economies of various nations, the attraction of foreign investment, and science—which is confirmed by the acceleration of the exchange of scientific and technological achievements and the support for the countries' scientific and technological development—are just a few of the many positive aspects of globalization, an objective process of the development of the world economy. Globalization is the process of integrating and unifying the world's economies, politics, and cultures. The primary characteristics are the global division of labor, the unrestricted flow of capital, labor, and production resources, the standardization of laws, business practices, and technical advancements, as well as the blending and convergent of cultural traditions from other nations. It is an objective process and has a systemic nature that covers all areas of society. The primary characteristics are the global division of labor, the unrestricted flow of capital, labor, and production resources, the standardization of laws, business practices, and technical advancements, as well as the blending and convergent of cultural traditions from other nations. It is a systematic procedure that is objective and affects every aspect of society. Additionally, there are anti-globalization movements that acknowledge the drawbacks of globalization. Such a group, alliance, or movement might comprise several anti-globalists like Green and AntiDaos. The stage of regionalization must be passed through in order to reach the level of globalization.

Processes that are integrated into globalization. According to A. Ochildiev, "...in the most general sense, globalization, on the one hand, means that a certain event, process, covers all regions, states, and the whole Earth, and on the other hand, it means that they affect the fate of mankind." In the words of V.I. Danilov-Danilyan, "Globalization is a concept

that stems not from logic, but from a historical paradigm. The interdependence of the many parts of globalization is not clearly and explicitly analyzed, he claimed. The definitions given above demonstrate how the complexity and variety of the globalization process set it apart. Because of this, S. Otamuratov stated that "...opinions about the concept of globalization continue to vary. That is normal. New opportunities are emerging in the influence it has on the transformation of the world since its characteristics of occurrence in space and time are distinct. On the cusp of the 1980s and 1990s, the term "globalization" received a new interpretation: the relatively recent aspects of the growth of the global economy from the use of this term, which was coined by the eminent American economist K. Ome, a native of Japan, and descriptions started to be applied to show its current state, which differs from its early stages of development.

Regrettably, wars have characterized human society for the entirety of its history. For a very long time, people have believed that war is a necessary, unavoidable, and even positive development for people. The writings of N. Machiavelli, F. Venon, T. Hobbes, J. Proudhon, F. Nietzsche, and others provide numerous examples of this. This does not imply that all ancient philosophers viewed war in the same light. It is generally documented how war affected minds like Erasmus of Rotterdam, J. J. Rousseau, Immanuel Kant, M. V. Lomonosov, and many more. The pursuit of peace in the 19th and 20th centuries was embodied in pacifism, or the complete rejection of all things associated to militarism and conflict. It is important to underline that wars grew bloodier and more horrific from century to century. In the 17th century, 3 million people perished in conflicts in Europe; 5.2 million perished in battles in the 19th century (of which around 2 million perished in the Napoleonic wars). In this sense, the 20th century was superior than all others. The First World War claimed the lives of almost 10 million people, which is comparable to the 200-year span of wars before it. During World War II, 60 million people died. It involved 61 nations and accounted for 80% of the world's population, including colonies. Military activities took place on the soil of 40 nations in Europe, Asia, and Africa as well as in the waters of the four oceans. The development of types of weapons of mass destruction (nuclear, hydrogen, neutron, chemical, bacteriological, etc.) has led to the fact that the stockpile of weapons accumulated today is enough to destroy humanity and all living things on our planet several times. It can be said that the problem of war and peace is "historically the first global problem of our time and remains the most dangerous and irrevocable problem at the top of the list of global problems." The end of the "Cold War", the elimination of the military-political conflict between the blocs, and the general improvement of the international situation have significantly reduced the risk of consciously starting a war. However, the risk of accidental initiation remains. Therefore, this global problem can be solved only through global disarmament and, first of all, the elimination of weapons of mass destruction.

As a contemporary phenomena, globalization accomplishes its goal in any way. Of course, even if some well-known and little-known forces — who could be called the

forerunners of globalization — artificially accelerate or become interested in this process, the spirituality, mentality, change, or strengthening of the nations — as mentioned above — depends, in part, on the nation itself to maintain its distinctiveness.

The Sustainable Development Goals are a call to global action to end poverty on Earth, protect the environment and climate, and ensure that all people around the world enjoy peace and prosperity. The goals that the UN is trying to achieve in Uzbekistan are:

- ending extreme poverty;
- ending hunger;
- health and well-being;
- quality education;
- gender equality;
- clean water and sanitation;
- cheap and clean energy;
- decent jobs and economic growth;
- industrialization, innovation and infrastructure;
- reducing inequality;
- sustainable cities and residential areas;
- responsible consumption and production
- fight against climate change
- protection of marine ecosystems;
- preservation of terrestrial ecosystems
- peace, justice and effective governance;
- cooperation for sustainable development

In conclusion, it should be said that globalization is a factor that contributes greatly to the development of man and society. We need to think philosophically about every innovation of globalization, adapt it to our own mentality, and then apply it to society. The reason we need to think philosophically is that philosophy is a science that comes from wise thoughts and opinions.

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